

TABLE

D.T.G. curve reading (in °C)	The compound formed and the loss in weight in T.G.A. curve	Nature inflexion point of the peak in D.T.A. curve in °C
60-140	$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4]$ 24mg	Endo at 130
150-240	$[\text{O}\{\{\text{Cr}_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4\}\}]$ 37mg	Endo at 240
240-310	$[\text{O}\{\{\text{Cr}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2\}\}]$ 237mg	Endo at 270
310-470	$[\text{Cr}_2\text{O}(\text{CO}_3)_2]$ 331mg	Exo at 360 Endo at 460
470-600	Cr_2O_3 391mg	Exo at 550 Endo at 600

Endo=Endothermal peak, Exo=Exothermal peak.

I. R. Spectra, Magnetic, U. V. and Visible Reflectance Spectra :

The i.r. spectra of the complex was carried out in nujol mull, magnetic and reflectance spectra were taken in solid phase at room temperature. The i.r. spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})_2(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ exhibits a strong and broad band at 3450 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at 960 cm^{-1} attributed to bridged hydroxyl group in the complex¹⁰. The broadening of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration at 1595 cm^{-1} and splitting of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ vibrations into two bands 1370 cm^{-1} and 1308 cm^{-1} indicates that some of the salicylic acid molecules are coordinated to Cr(III) atoms through both the carboxylic and phenolic oxygen while the rest are monocoordinated. The medium bands at 1620 cm^{-1} and 808 cm^{-1} are attributed to coordinated water molecules.

The magnetic moment value of the complex was found to be 3.45 B.M. The electronic reflectance spectra exhibit two bands at 16390 cm^{-1} and 23810 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g(\text{F})}$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g(\text{F})}$ transitions respectively in octahedral ligand field. The lower magnetic value¹¹ and 10 Dq value^{12,13} in the present case might be due to bridged nature of weak ligand field energy of salicylate group.

Oxidation :

The very sharp inflexion obtained at 3.8 ml after 3 hrs storage at room temperature corresponding to 10 electron abstraction stage per molecule of salicylic acid and the i.r. spectra indicate the destruction of aromatic ring. The intermediate stage could not be identified. At 12 hrs storage at room temperature a very sharp inflexion point was obtained at 5.0 ml i.e., 14 electron abstraction per salicylic acid molecule. The products obtained at this stage were characterised as *bis*(maleato)diaquo chromium(III) and *bis*(oxalato)diaquo chromium(III) complex as intermediate products spectrophotometrically and by paper chromatography. On prolonged storage at room temperature (240 hrs) inflexion point was obtained at 7.8 ml corresponding to 22 electron abstraction. The oxidation product of coordinated salicylate was identified to be predominantly *cis-bis*(oxalate)

diaquo chromium(III). The complete oxidation of coordinated salicylate to carbon dioxide and water takes place only after heating at 90° for 18 hrs.

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Synthesis of 5-Hydroxy-3', 4', 5', 7-Tetramethoxy-8-Prenylflavanone

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5-HYDROXY-3', 4', 5', 7-tetramethoxy-8-prenylflavanone has been synthesised by a new route, involving lesser number of steps and in better yield, starting from 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone¹ which on prenylation gave two compounds, identified as 4-*o*-methyl-3-prenylphloroacetophenone(I) and gem-di-C-prenyl-4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone(II) on the basis of spectral data. Ketone (I) on condensation with 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde² under alkaline conditions gave the title compound (III) which agreed in its characteristics with the sample prepared earlier³ by a different route. Methylation of III yielded IV which was also made from the corresponding chalcone⁴(V).

Experimental

Prenylation of 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone :

To an ice cold solution of 4-*o*-methylphloroacetophenone (5 g) in alcoholic KOH (3g in 50 ml)

was added prenyl bromide (5 g) and the reaction mixture stirred for 24 hr at room temperature. Work up of the product followed by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-benzene mixture gave ketones(I) and (II), with the latter coming out first.

I

III; R = H

IV; R = CH₃

II

V

I: (3-Prenyl-4-o-methylphloroacetophenone), yellow needles; m. p. 125-6°; dark brown ferric reaction; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1635 cm^{-1} ; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{MeOH}}$: 290, 325 (3.91, 3.12) nm; NMR (δ , CDCl_3): 1.8 (s, 6H, gem dimethyl), 2.69 (s, 3H, $-\text{COCH}_3$), 3.3 (d, $J=7\text{Hz}$, 2H, ArCH_2-), 3.9 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 5.15 (m, 1H, olefinic proton), 5.98 (s, 1H, aromatic proton), 9.2 (s, 1H, C_2-OH), 11.4 (s, 1H, C_6-OH). (Found: C, 67.0; H, 7.5. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 67.2; 7.25%).

II: (Gem-di-C-prenyl-4-o-methylphloroacetophenone), colourless plates; m.p. 68°; orange-red ferric reaction; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1650-1400 (br), 1215 cm^{-1} ;

$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{MeOH}}$: 260, 270, 310 (4.02, 4.02, 4.32) nm; NMR (δ , CDCl_3): 1.55 (s, 12H, four methyl of two prenyl groups), 2.45-2.75 (m, 7H, $-\text{COCH}_3$ & $2 \times \text{ArCH}_2-$), 3.75 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.75 (t, 2H, olefinic protons of two prenyl groups), 5.5 (s, 1H, ring proton), 18.4 (s, 1H, D_2O exchanged, $-\text{OH}$). (Found: C, 71.9; H, 8.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 71.7; H, 8.17%).

5-Hydroxy-3', 4', 5', 7-tetramethoxy-8-prenylflavanone(III):

To an ice cold solution of I (400 mg) in 20 ml of 25% alcoholic KOH was added 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde (360 mg) and the mixture was kept

at 0° for 24 hr. The product, which was found to be a mixture of a flavanone and the unreacted ketone, was subjected to preparative TLC over silica gel using benzene-acetone (9 : 1) as developing solvent. The flavanone crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles; m. p. 150-51° (lit⁸ m. p. 150-51°); green ferric reaction and negative Gibbs test; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1625 cm^{-1} , $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{MeOH}}$: 290, 335 (4.10, 3.50); with AlCl_3 , 315, 365; with AlCl_3+HCl , 315, 365, with NaOMe , 290, 360 nm; NMR (δ , CDCl_3) 1.65 (s, 6H, gem dimethyl), 2.95 (m, 2H, H-3), 3.25 (d, $J=7\text{Hz}$, 2H, ArCH_2-), 3.9 (s, 12H, 4x $-\text{OCH}_3$), 5.3 (m, 2H, H-2 and olefinic proton of prenyl group), 6.14 (s, 1H, H-6), 6.73 (s, 2H, H-2' & 6'), 12.10 (s, 1H, OH). (Found: C, 67.1; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 67.3; H, 6.59%).

5,7,3',4',5'-Pentamethoxy-8-prenylflavanone (IV):

(a) To a solution of flavanone(III, 40 mg) in dry acetone (5 ml) was added anhydrous K_2CO_3 (1 g) and dimethylsulphate (0.2 ml).

The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr. The product obtained after standard workup was purified by preparative TLC. It gave colourless needles; m.p. 170-71°; negative ferric reaction; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1660 cm^{-1} ;

$\lambda_{\max}^{\text{MeOH}}$: 290, 320 nm; NMR (δ , CDCl_3): 1.65 (s, 6H, gem dimethyl), 2.9 (m, 2H, H-3), 3.3 (m, 2H, ArCH_2), 4.1 (s, 9H, 3x $-\text{OCH}_3$), 4.15 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 4.2 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 5.5 (m, 2H, H-2 & olefinic proton), 6.15 (s, 1H, H-6), 6.7 (s, 2H, H-2' & 6'). (Found: C, 67.6; H, 7.2. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_7$ requires C, 67.8; H, 6.9%).

(b) The chalcone⁴ (V, 50 mg) was cyclised, by heating with pyridine (1 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) at 60° for 11 hr, into a flavanone which was found to be identical with IV in all respects (co-TLC, mmp, superimposable IR).

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